

THE CONCEPT OF THE AMERICAN DREAM AND WALT WHITMAN

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Abstract. It is obviously difficult to learn about "What is American dream?" and "What is the connection between America and Walt Whitman?". This article gives you some main points about them. Throughout American history, there have been critics of its national ethos. Some critics point out that American focus on individualism and capital results in materialism, consumerism and a lack of worker solidarity.

Key words: democracy, rights, liberty, social mobility, equality, "Leaves of Grass"

The American Dream is the national ethos of the United States, a set of ideals including representative democracy, rights, liberty, and equality, in which freedom is interpreted as the opportunity for individual prosperity and success, as well as upward social mobility for oneself and their children, achieved through hard work in a capitalist society with few barriers. The term "American Dream" was coined by James Truslow Adams in 1931, saying that "life should be better and richer and fuller for everyone, with opportunity for each according to ability or achievement" regardless of social class or circumstances of birth .

Proponents of the American Dream often claim that its tenets originate from the United States Declaration of Independence, which states that "all men are created equal" with the right to "life, liberty, and the pursuit of happiness" . The Preamble to the U.S. Constitution is used similarly. It states that the Constitution's purpose is to, in part, "secure the Blessings of Liberty to ourselves and our Posterity".

Throughout American history, there have been critics of its national ethos. Some critics point out that American focus on individualism and capital results in materialism, consumerism and a lack of worker solidarity. In 2015, only 10.5 percent of American workers were members of a labor union . The American Dream has also been criticized as a product of American exceptionalism, as it does not acknowledge the hardships many Americans face, namely in regards to the legacies of American slavery and Native American genocide, as well as other examples of discriminatory violence .

After reading Walt Whitman's great celebration of America, how can things go so wrong? After Song of Myself, how could we forget who we are and

who we can be? Maybe we didn't read it. Maybe we need to read it again. A current slogan stirs the pot of political nostalgia: Make America Great Again. Whitman would be fine with the first three words. The fourth word would trouble him. Whitman's America was already great, not perfect, but great. Whitman's gaze was not back to the 'good old days.' America's glory lay in its recognition of national imperfections and the hard work to correct them.

Whitman celebrated the can-do American spirit exhibited in its great cities, its railroads, canals, ports, factories, and its brawny laborer force who made the engine of economy run. But for Whitman the American dream was about more than making ourselves secure and comfortable. His dream gave encouragement to individuals to go deep as well as far, to draw from the unfathomable wells of pleasure and knowledge which is everyone's right.

Whitman's America, like the America of the founders, was the manifestation of a great idea. It was not intended to be a nation built for a certain class, or race, or religion. It was not to fulfill the destiny of 'a' people, das Volk, people just like me. America chose a harder and higher task, making a nation out of people who are not just like me; e pluribus unam – many formed into one. The intention was to create a nation dedicated to maximizing opportunity for all. Of course, we got off to a shaky and historically determined start. But the question calling us to greatness has been and remains; who is included in the 'all' when we recite with hand over heart, 'with liberty and justice for all.'

At our best, the American story has been distinguished by expansion, not contraction.

At our best, the American story has been distinguished by inclusion, not exclusion.

At our best, the American story has been distinguished by plurality, not singularity.

At our best, the American story has been distinguished by diversity, not uniformity.

Our national story is the enlargement of who is included in the all.

We see this inclusion as strength, not weakness.

May this continue to be our reason for being America.

The ideological impact of the American Dream is enormous and unpredictable. The concept can evoke many diverse emotions, especially in creative people such as poets. Walt Whitman and Langston Hughes, two prominent figures of American poetry of the past, are of them. "I Hear America Singing," "I, Too,"

“Harlem,” and “The Negro Speaks of Rivers” are the emotional responses to the American Dream and societal processes relevant to those times. This work will analyze these 4 four poems representing the two sides of the United States (US) society, those who are already part of the American Dream and those who want to become one.

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